

TECHNOLOGY OF USING EXERCISES TO DEVELOP CRITICAL THINKING IN HIGH SCHOOL ENGLISH CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Critical Thinking is a rating system that is used to analyze things and events with the formulation of reasonable conclusions and allows learner to make informed judgments, interpretations, and correctly apply results to situations and problems. The article analyzes the techniques and methods of using the technology for the development of critical thinking through reading and writing. When using this technology in the classroom, the learner can use such techniques as a cluster, a basket of ideas, an insert which can be often used as reflection.

Critical Thinking is a rating system that is used to analyze things and events with the formulation of reasonable conclusions and allows learners to make informed judgments, interpretations and apply correctly results to situations and problems. There is a more detailed definition - "intellectually ordered a process of actively and skillfully analyzing, conceptualizing, applying, synthesizing and or evaluation of information obtained or generated by observation, experience, reflection or communication, as guidelines for beliefs and actions"[5].

Critical thinking skills cannot develop spontaneously. The teacher must manage this process. Lessons contribute to the development of Critical thinking with the help variety of materials and interactive approaches. Self-awareness is an important role in this process. Through

Critical thinking and self-awareness, learner can understand the connection between thoughts and emotions. Although it is generally accepted that they are independent of each other, the feelings are based on a certain level of thinking, and thoughts that appear at a certain level of feelings [4].

The technology of critical thinking is based on three phases of the lesson:

- **Call phase (Evocation)** - where the existing knowledge is updated and awakening interest in the new topic, as well as setting the student's own goals, learning.
- **The Realization** of meaning phase in which the obtaining new information and adjusting the students' goals.
- **The Reflection phase** includes reflection as well as staging new goals and objectives.

When using this technology in the classroom, foreign language teachers must teach students beyond language skills. A critical approach to learning must also be developed, increase their desire for new knowledge. Working on this technology should be well aware of that the work will be productive if the material is chosen correctly, contributing directly to the development of critical thinking and methods [3]. Application of techniques of critical thinking technology in teaching practice, the English language of schoolchildren proves the effectiveness and appropriateness of their introduction into the process of teaching a foreign language at secondary and senior schools of study.

What is included in the concept of "Critical thinking" in high English classes? -The set of key skills required for critical thinking include observation, the ability to interpret, analyze, draw conclusions, and make judgments. Critical thinking applies logic and also relies on meta-knowledge and broad criteria of intelligence such as clarity, believability, accuracy, meaningfulness, depth, outlook, and fairness. Emotionality, creative imagination, value attitudes are also integral parts of critical thinking [4].

Critical thinking is understood as the process of assessing the reliability, accuracy or value of something, the ability to assess and find reasons and alternative points of view, perceive the situation as a whole and change one's position based on facts and arguments. It is also called logical or analytical thinking. The children have been trained for unambiguity of definitions, classifications and views on the same problem, and how important it is for them to learn to understand that the lack of

uniqueness is often not a disadvantage or a problem, but, on the contrary, a good opportunity to penetrate deeper into the essence of things, more discover.

Critical Thinking Skills in high school learners - In order to using learner's critical thinking, it is important for him to develop a number of qualities, among which D. Halpern highlights:

- *Willingness to plan.* Thoughts are often chaotic. It is important to arrange them, build a sequence of presentation. The orderliness of thought is a sign of confidence.

- *Flexibility.* If a student is not ready to perceive the ideas of others, he will never be able to become a generator of his own ideas and thoughts. Flexibility allows learner to wait with judgment until the student has a variety of information.

- *Perseverance.* Often, when facing with a difficult task, teachers and learners postpone its solution until later. By developing perseverance in straining the mind, the student will certainly achieve much better learning results.

- *Willingness to correct their mistakes.* A critically thinking person will not justify their wrong decisions, but draw conclusions, use the mistake to continue learning.

- *Awareness.* This is a very important quality, which presupposes the ability to observe oneself in the process of mental activity, to track the course of reasoning.

- *Search for compromise solutions.* It is important that the decisions made are perceived by other people, otherwise they will remain at the level of statements.

D. Halpern reflects on the intellectual skills of critical thinking, draws attention to the following of them [2]:

- analysis / conclusions;

- nomination, formulation, development of hypotheses;
- establishment and creation, search for analogies, metaphors;
- activation of previously acquired knowledge;
- activation of cause-and-effect relationships;
- analysis of significance;
- comparison - contrast - opposition;
- application in real condition;
- argumentation;
- assessment and its reliability / validity;
- generalization of ideas;
- exploring other points of view.

Usage of critical thinking technology in high school English lessons - Foreign language lessons contribute to the development of critical thinking through a variety of materials and interactive approaches. The technology for the development of critical thinking through reading and writing stands out among innovative pedagogical ideas by a successful combination of problematization and productivity of learning with the adaptability of the lesson, effective methods and techniques. Using the "Critical Thinking" technology in foreign language lessons, the teacher develops the student's personality, first of all, through direct teaching of a foreign language, resulting in the formation of communicative competence, which provides comfortable conditions for cognitive activity and self-improvement [3]. The teacher stimulates the interests of the student, develops his desire to practically use a foreign language, as well as to learn, thereby making it real to achieve success in mastering the subject.

A teacher working in the framework of critical thinking technology should be well

aware that his work will be productive if he is correctly chosen:

- informative material contributing to the development of critical thinking;
- method (separate technique, strategy) of the lesson.

Brainstorming technique - This technique is well known to the teacher and does not need a detailed description. However, since it is widely used in the classroom, it is advisable to clarify some of the procedural aspects of its implementation. The main goal of "educational brainstorming" is the development of a creative type of thinking [8]. Consequently, the choice of a topic for its implementation directly depends on the number of possible solutions to a particular problem. "Training brainstorming" is usually carried out in groups of 5-7 people.

The first stage is the creation of range of ideas, possible solutions to the problem. Any suggestions are accepted and fixed on the board or poster. Criticism and commenting are not allowed. Time limit - up to 15 minutes.

The second stage is a collective discussion of ideas and proposals. At this stage, the main thing is to find the rational in any of the sentences, to try to combine them into a whole.

The third stage is the selection of the most promising solutions from the point of view of the currently available resources. This stage can even be postponed in time and carried out in the next lesson.

Clustering - the selection of semantic units of the text and their graphic design in a certain order in the form of a bunch. Clusters can become a leading technique both at the stage of challenge, reflection, and a lesson strategy as a whole. Making some notes, sketches for memory, we often

intuitively distribute them in a special way, arrange them into categories. Cluster - a graphic technique for organizing material. The rules are very simple. In the center is our theme, and around it are large semantic units [1]. The cluster system encompasses more information than we get in normal work. This technique can be applied at the stage of the challenge, when we systematize the information received before acquaintance with the main source (text) in the form of questions or headings of semantic blocks. This technique has great potential at the stage of reflection: correcting incorrect assumptions in preliminary clusters, filling them in based on new information. A very important stage is the presentation of new clusters. The task of this work is not only the systematization of the material, but also the establishment of cause-and-effect relationships between the "clusters" [6].

Concept wheel - The conceptual wheel technique can be effectively used at the stage of a call. Students need to choose synonyms for the word located in the core of the conceptual "wheel" and write in the sectors of the wheel. For instance: *like, love, to be fond of, enjoy, to be keen on, get pleasure with, prefer.*

"Thin" and "thick" questions table can be used in any of the three stages of the lesson. If we use this technique at the challenge stage, then these will be questions that our students would like to receive answers to while studying the topic. Students are encouraged to formulate questions to the topic in the form of "thin" and "thick" questions. Next, the teacher writes down a series of questions on the board and asks the students (individually or in groups) to try to answer them, arguing their assumptions. As you

work with the table, questions are written in the left column that require a simple monosyllabic answer. In the right column, questions are written that require a detailed, detailed answer; or questions to which they themselves cannot yet answer, but would like to find answers to them. After answers to these questions are heard, students are invited to read or listen to the text, find confirmation of their assumptions and answers to the "thin" and "thick" questions. At the stage of comprehending the content, the technique serves to actively fix questions in the course of reading, listening; in reflection - to demonstrate understanding of the past. At the stage of reflection, the task is to compose another 3-4 "thin" and "thick" questions, put them in the table, work with questions in pairs, choosing the most interesting ones that can be asked to the whole class [7].

Who...?, What...?, When...?, Where...?, Was it...?, What was the name...?, Are you agree that...? etc., Why...? Explain why...?, Why do you think that...?, What is the most important idea of the story?, What is the difference between...?, If you were... would you...?etc.

Zigzag - The purpose of this technique is to study and systematize a large volume of material. To do this, you must first break the text into semantic fragments for mutual learning. The number of passages should match the number of group members. For example, if the text is divided into 5 semantic passages, then in groups (let's call them conditionally workers) - 5 people.

1. In this strategy, there may not be a call phase as such, since the task itself - the organization of work with a large volume of text - itself serves as a challenge.

2. Semantic stage. The class is divided into groups. The group is given texts of various contents. Each student works with his own text: highlighting the main thing, he either composes a pivotal summary, or uses one of the graphic forms (for example, "cluster"). At the end of the work, students move to other groups - expert groups.

3. Stage of reflection: work in a group of "experts". New groups are formed so that each group includes "specialists" on the same topic. In the process of sharing the results of their work, a general presentation scheme of the story on the topic is drawn up. The question of who will conduct the final presentation is being decided. The students then move to their original groups. Returning to his working group, the expert introduces the other members of the group to his topic, using a general presentation scheme. In the group, information is exchanged between all members of the working group. Thus, in each working group, thanks to the work of experts, a general understanding of the topic under study is formed.

4. The next step will be the presentation of information on individual topics, which is carried out by one of the experts, others make additions, answer questions. Thus, there is a "second hearing" of the topic [8].

The result of the lesson can be a research or creative assignment on the topic studied. This technique is also used on texts of a smaller volume. In this case, the text is studied by all students, the principle of dividing into groups - questions to this text, their number should coincide with the

number of group members. Expert groups gather specialists on one issue: for a more detailed study of it, exchange of views, preparation of a detailed answer to a question, and discussion of the form of its presentation. Returning to the working groups, the experts consistently present their answers to their questions.

In conclusion, a teacher who wants to teach critical thinking should observe how students receive knowledge, and not how they simply reproduce it. Acquiring knowledge requires certain thinking skills such as analytical, problematic, critical, creative, reflective thinking. How can critical thinking be applied to teaching foreign language? Critical thinking skills cannot be developed spontaneously. The teacher must manage this process. Foreign language lessons contribute to the development of critical thinking through a variety of materials and interactive approaches. Self-awareness plays an important role in this process. Through critical thinking and self-awareness, the connection between thoughts and emotions can be understood. Although it is generally accepted that they are independent of each other, in fact, feelings are based on a certain level of thought and thoughts appear at a certain level of feelings. The foreign language teacher can contribute critical thinking in the lesson with helping students with understanding themselves and the world around them: to deal with perceptions, assumptions, prejudices, values, break old habits in order to create a new point of view.

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